

**WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFECTIVE USE OF FINANCIAL AND
ECONOMIC RESOURCES OF BUKHARA REGION.**

Kudratov Muhammad Rustamovich

Teacher of the Economics Department of
Bukhara State University

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The financial system of the society is a unique importance of the leading financial mechanism, which is one of the most important mechanisms that will choose social and economic regulation of the government and the state and economic regulation of the state in the formation and development of the state, which is the development of social and economic regulation of the leading society today. lib, its main level is the state budget. The state budget is a major centralized money fund of the state and is an economic category based on the implementation of functions of the state. Budget word is meant by the treasury, as well as the establishment of centralized cash funds in the government and the expenses related to the implementation of the state's policy.

The economic power of each country is expressed by the fact that it has a perfect budget. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the main document defining the foundations of budget relations in the country. Article 122 of it specifies the structure of the state budget.

However, a single law that summarizes and regulates in detail all stages of the budget process has not yet been developed. This makes it difficult to implement institutional changes in the financial sector in the conditions of the market economy, and to bring the budget relations into line with international standards. The adoption of the Law "On the budget system of the Republic of Uzbekistan" can be considered an important step in the improvement of this system. The budget financial policy is primarily aimed at ensuring the full functioning of the market mechanism in our republic. Decentralized direction plays a key role in budget financing.

According to preliminary data, in 2019, the volume of the gross domestic product (GDP) of the Republic of Uzbekistan at current prices is 511,838.1 billion. amounted to soum and increased by 5.6% compared to 2018. The GDP deflator index was 119.2% compared to the prices of 2018.

The experience of developed countries shows that since the 60s and 70s of the last century, as a result of the high rates of economic growth, there has been an increase in state expenses. Therefore, in a number of countries, budgets incorporating medium- and long-term perspective indicators were drawn up. Because it reflects the state's need for future expenditures.

According to the results of 2019, the volume of GDP calculated at the average annual exchange rate of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan is 57,907 million. amounted to US dollars (in 2018 - 50,397 million US dollars). For information: the official exchange rate of the US dollar against the soum was equal to 8,069 soums in 2018 and 8,839 soums in 2019. GDP per capita amounted to 15,242,000 soums (or the equivalent of 1,724 US dollars), and this figure increased by 3.6% compared to 2018. GDP per capita growth was 2.7% and 3.6% in 2017 and 2018, respectively.

One of the components of the state financial system - regional finance - meeting the needs of the region occupies an important place. Regional finance ensures the implementation of activities aimed at meeting the social-cultural and communal-household needs of the population. Therefore, regional finance is a system of economic relations for the distribution of funds aimed at the economic and social development of the region. Through regional finance, the state actively conducts its social policy in the region. On the basis of the allocation of these funds to the budgets of regional governments, municipal public education, health care, communal and household services are financed. This will expand the range of activities to be carried out. Not only secondary schools, but also higher education institutions, healthcare systems, environmental protection and other facilities are financed from regional budgets. One of the components of regional funds is the funds of economic entities. These funds are, firstly, from the funds of communal and household enterprises owned by the municipality, secondly, from the funds of enterprises and firms that provide services to social, cultural and household objects, and thirdly, from extra-budgetary funds (bond funds lari, voluntary contributions, etc.) are organized.

The basis of local finance is the local budget. The Republic of Uzbekistan includes income and expenses of local authorities. For example, in the USA, Germany, and Japan, 50-60 percent of state financial resources are contributed by local finance, which shows how important it is in the economic life of society. In many countries, local transport, water and gas supply, school, hospital and housing construction, urban maintenance, communal economy, police, etc. are financed from the local budget. 684 125.0 mln. by enterprises and organizations in economic sectors in Bukhara region in January-November 2020. the final financial result was obtained in the amount of soums. Compared to the same period last year, the profit increased by 177,994.3 million soums or 35.2%.

Final financial results of economic activities in Bukhara region in 2020.

	<i>Profit, loss (-), mln. Soum</i>	<i>in percentage compared to 2019</i>
Total	684 125,0	135,2
Mining industry and operation of open mines	1 143,2	96,4
Manufacturing industry	643 201,2	145,2
Supply of electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning	15 569,4	x
Construction	13 047,4	3,1 m.
Trade	48 503,2	93,9
Transport and storage	-26 164,7	x
Accommodation and food services	1 708,5	68,4
Transactions with real estate	816,7	79,9
Professional, scientific and technical activity	1 792,4	2,6 m.
Provision of management activities and support services	37,7	18,1
Providing health care and social services	89,6	38,7
Others	-15 619,6	-

In January-November 2020, compared to the same period of the previous year, the main increase in profit was achieved by "Dori-Darmon" JSC (1659.5 million soums), "Uzbekipaksanoat yuushmasi" JSC (123.2 million soums), "Uzbekneftegaz" JSC (200,213.3 million soums), "Uzdonmahsulot" JSC (1761.3 million soums), Land resources, geodesy, cartography of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the state cadastre belongs to the state committee (987.4 million soums). In terms of regions, the main part of the profit is 637,632.0 mln. 5,903.2 million soums for Karakol district and 11,566.9 million soums for the city of Kogon. In January-November 2020, 9 enterprises and organizations received 64,524.8 mln. caused a loss of soums.

Final financial results by region in 2020

	<i>Profit, loss (-), mln. soum</i>	<i>2019 year in percentage compared to January-November</i>
Bukhara region	684 125,0	135,2
Bukhara city	9 896,1	24,8
Kagan city.	11 566,9	3,1 m.
Bukhara	-748,0	x
Vobkent	1 353,1	82,8
Jondor	5 163,1	42,9
Kagan	1 593,9	x
Olot	4 196,7	x
Peshku	1 789,9	140,3
Romitan	1 075,3	180,2
Shofirkon	1 079,4	110,1
Qorako'l	5 903,2	100,5
Qorovulbozor	637 632,0	145,8
Gijduvan	3 623,4	80,4

The main part of the loss is 16,891.7 mln. soums (26.2% of the total loss), "Uzbekistan textile and sewing and knitting industrial enterprises association" 10670.5 mln. soums (16.5 percent), "Uzbekistan Airports" JSC 32,520.8 million soums (50.4 percent) and 4,441.8 million soums soums (6.9 percent) correspond to enterprises of other sectors.

In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Taxes", the main distributive funds of regional budgets include: tax on added premium, excise duties, payments at specified rates from the income of regional enterprises established by law.

Payments for distributive incomes are determined by regional governments. Distributive income plays a key role in the development of the region.

The role of distributive funds serves not only the financial support of the governments for the development of the region, but also the increase of

payments to the higher budgets, and the increase of the efficiency of the regional economy.

Due to the fact that the rate of expenditure is higher than the rate of income in some cases, subsidies from the budget are sometimes needed. It should be noted that grants and subsidies hardly change the development of the economy. They do not have the qualities of encouragement, they only create a feeling of patronage in the regional administrations.

